

IDENTIFICATION AND MODELLING OF DAMAGE MECHANISMS IN SHORT GLASS FIBRE REINFORCED POLYPROPYLENE COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a study of damage and damage mechanisms in Short-Glass-Fibre-Reinforced Polypropylene (SGFRP). The initiation and the growth of damage occur according to complex failure mechanisms, which are widely dependent on material structure and also on the loading conditions. The use of acoustic emission (AE) and the scanning electronic microscopy (SEM) observations is proved to be useful for this damage investigation. Using the results of this experimental approach, a micromechanical modelling of the damage effects is proposed. The developed model has allowed us to integrate non-linearity of material behaviour and thus to obtain a good agreement between the simulated and the experimental curves.

INTRODUCTION

Short fibres reinforcement composite materials such as granules long fibres (GLF) containing fibres of 150 mm of length are attractive materials because of their mechanical performances (failure, impact). These materials are characterised by a progressive degradation phase which occurred as by microstructural changes called damage. The study of damage mechanisms is relatively recent. If basic mechanisms such matrix, fibre and the interface fibre/matrix failure are well identified, their interaction remains an area of research. This interaction depends on geometrical, mechanical and structural parameters of the composite material constituents. In the first part of this study, an experimental approach has been developed in the aim to identify and to follow these damage modes. Previous studies on different composite materials [1], [4-5] have allowed to set up a schematic model of acoustic emission. This model assigns amplitude of signals emitted by materials under different solicitations to damage mechanisms. Applied this experimental methodology to SGFRP, has allowed us a continuous monitoring of damage growth under tensile tests. This analysis has also allowed us to highlight the complementary aspect of amplitudes distribution and microscopic observations. From this study, it emphasizes that the main initiator mechanism of the material ruin, is the interface fibre/matrix failure. This damage mode induces a fibre pull-out reducing strongly the mechanical properties of composite. The second part of the problem deals with the modelling of the damaged behaviour of this material. It is a micromechanical approach based on the Mori-Tanaka's model using the Eshelby equivalent inclusion theory. This model has been adapted and modified, in the aim to integrate damage mechanisms and to estimate their influence on the overall material behaviour. This integration of the damage mechanisms has required the introduction of the notion of participation of a mechanism (i) to a phase (j) noted (P_i^j), whose its evolution is evaluated experimentally using the acoustic emission techniques and the experimental schematic Model. The stiffness prediction tool thus developed presents an interaction between the two approaches of the problem (Experimental and Numerical). It allows then to predict the overall elasticity tensors of the damaged material by integrating their microstructural aspects. The identification of an evolution function $F(\beta)$, defined explicitly, allows to assign the evolution of the damage parameter (β) to the applied macro stress and thus to simulate mechanical tests such as the tensile test. The comparison between numerical and experimental results shows the good agreement and confirms the experimental methodology.

EXPERIMENT

MATERIALS

The materials used in this study were various granular long fibre composites. Manufacture of material consists of extruding the granulates (Fibre, polypropylene) through on extruder with a low compression ratio in order to avoid fibre failure. Then the material is poured manually into a mould where it is compressed at (25 MPa).The final product from which the specimens are cut is a disc of thickness 2.5 mm. Fibre length is 150 mm and the aspect ratio ($\alpha=l/d$) is equal 9400. This material contain 40% (by weight) of short glass fibres.

TENSILE TESTS

Tensile tests have been performed at room temperature (between 20° and 25°), with a relative humidity of approximately 50%. The static tests have been carried out on an INSTRON 1186 tensile test machine with a displacement speed of 1 mm/mn.

ACOUSTIC EMISSION TECHNIQUES

The damage growth detection and monitoring have been performed by using the amplitude analysis of Acoustic Emission signals generated during the advent of a damage mechanisms. The acquisition and the processing of the acoustic activity have been carried out by means of an acoustic emission system (DUNEGANE / ENDEVCO 3000) possessing the next physical characteristics:

- Preamplifier Gain 39 dB
- Preamplifier Filters : 450 B and 190 B (according to the used pack)
- A.E Threshold : Selectable, it is fixed to 30 dB for the study.
- Interval of amplitude channels is from 0 to 100 dB.
- Channel Width (Resolution) 1 dB.
- Dead Time 1 msec. (Emission by bursts)

Acoustic Emission Signals are detected using a piezoelectric transducer (PAC MICROPHONE 80) and having larges rang frequencies going from 200 KHz to 1 MHZ.

A coupling fluid (Dough 428 Rhodorsil Silicone) is used so as to obtain a flawless contact between the transducer and the specimen.

The A.E investigation method is combined to the successive microscopique observations (using a Scanning Electron Microscope) at different stages of damage growth. It may contribute to a best comprehension of the advent and the evolution of the basic damage mechanisms.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

The tensile properties of the material are listed in table 1. This material present a less dispersion due to the shorter fibre length. This favours a global homogeneous material state which produces an overall, isotropic behaviour at the macroscopic level.

Table 1. Tensile mechanical properties of the material studied

Material	Tensile modulus (MPa)	Poisson Ratio	Damage threshold (MPa)	Max. Tensile Strength (MPa)
(SGFRP)	7292.1±555.45	0.34±0.03	35.6±4.3	90.38±6.58

The stress/strain curves in the tensile tests have a pronounced non-linearity which is in correlation with the early damaged state of this material and with the thermoplastic matrix (figure 1.)

Fig. 1. Stress-strain curves of the composites in tensile test.

DAMAGE MECHANISMS IDENTIFICATION.

In specimens subjected to tensile loading, the basic failure modes are identified by combination of two experimental techniques of damage investigation.

Using a piezoelectric sensor connected to an acquisition system, the acoustic emission has been recorded during tensile loading and analysed in terms of amplitude. Microscopic observations of damaged specimen allow to confirm the advent of each failure mechanism.

The details of methodology of the damage mechanisms discrimination are given in references [1],[4] and [5].

The different amplitude distributions have permitted to distinguish five areas on curves. Each one of these area is characterised by an interval of amplitudes values and associated to one or several basic damage modes. Typical amplitude distribution in tensile loading is illustrated in figure 2. The areas are defined as following.

Area 1 → Matrix Microcracking.

Area 2 → Matrix/Matrix friction and Delamination between packets.

Area 3 → Interface decohesion (Fibre/Matrix and between bundles).

Area 4 → Fibre/Matrix friction and fibre debonding.

Area 5 → Fibres breakage.

Fig. 2. Typical Amplitude Distribution and Areas definition

The damage and fracture process of this materials clearly begins by the matrix microcracking around the end of the fibres. Some interface failures occur and contribute to the generalized coalescence of all the microcracks. Figure 3 shows the coalescence of matrix cracking and interfaces debonding with at the end, fibre breakage. Figure 4 present interfaces mechanism failure with fibre pull-out phenomena. This mechanism is very important due to its effect on the material mechanical properties.

Fig.3. Failure mechanisms of Material.

Fig.4. Matrix failure with fibre sliding.

Successive amplitude distributions are presented in figure 5, which allow us to follow the damage evolution during stress increase (figure 6). So it is possible to follow the damage growth from these curves. After the first stage of matrix cracking, many interface fractures occur which are immediately followed by fibre pull-out.

Fig. 5. Acoustic Emission amplitude distribution.

Fig. 6. Stress/strain curve and AE amplitude distribution.

OTHER DAMAGE MECHANISMS CLASSIFICATION

In order to facilitate their modelling, basic failure mechanisms are classified according to the phase (matrix, interface or inclusion) brought into play during their appearance. This is besides their classification according to their interval of characteristic amplitudes [6]. In what follows, they are classified mainly according to two types: mechanisms relative to the matrix degradation, which represent initiation, coalescence and propagation of microcracks that will be designated: mechanisms of type (A). This first type includes matrix microcracking and pseudo-delamination. The second type of damage mechanisms are those linked to interfacial decohesion, fibre-matrix friction and fibre pull out processes considered as deriving processes. These are referred to as mechanisms of type (B).

EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION OF THE PARTICIPATION RATE (P_i^j)

The introduction of damage mechanisms in the calculation of the stiffness reduction requires the evaluation of each mechanism contribution to the ruin of the Representative Elementary Volume (REV). This evaluation is based on the results of the schematic model [5] presented in the foregoing sections. Indeed, in this classification an attribution of amplitude intervals of A.E events associated to one or several damage processes was established. Hence, An experimental parameter is defined, it represents the participation of the basic mechanism (i) in the failure of the REV, such as:

$$P_i^j = \frac{A_i^j}{A_{tot}} \quad (1)$$

$i = 1,5 \quad \text{and} \quad j = 1, 2, \dots$

Fig. 7. Schematic representation of experimental evaluation of the area associated to mechanism (1) at the phase (j).

- (i) represents the number of the basic mechanism and (j) indicates the phase damage considered.
- (A_i^j) is the area associated to the mechanism (i) at the phase (j), it is characterised by an interval of amplitude and a number of events (Fig 7.)
- (A_{tot}) is the total area of amplitude distribution, it corresponds to the final phase of damage.

EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION OF MICROCRACK DENSITY.

The integration the mechanisms of type (A) in the micromechanical model is based on the fact that a microcracks are considered as a new phase constituting the material. The mechanical properties of this new phase are known, it concerns a microcrack and therefore a null rigidity tensor. Furthermore, the concentration of these microcracks is determined according to the participation rate of the mechanisms (A) in the total failure of the REV. [6]

$$V_{\mu} = \frac{P_A}{1 + P_A} (1 - V_f) = \beta \quad (2)$$

(V_f) is the volume fraction of reinforcement.

(V_{μ}) is the volume fraction of the damaged matrix. (associated to microcracks density)

In the modelling, the microcrack is considered as an ellipsoidal inclusion with null rigidity. It is characterised by a density (V_{μ}) and also by an aspect ratio (α_{μ}).

MODELLING OF THE DAMAGE MECHANISMS.

MECHANISMS OF TYPE (A)

The infinite body containing misoriented short fibres and microcracks, subjected to the applied uniform macro stress (Σ) is considered. fibres are modelled as ellipsoidal inclusions of the same size and having (α_f) as aspect ratio. The REV designated by (D), contains fibres and microcracks randomly oriented in the plate plane and denoted by (Ω) and (Ω_μ) respectively. The elastic stiffness tensors of the isotropic matrix and fibre are denoted (C_m) and (C_f) respectively.

Due to the disturbance caused by the presence of all inclusions, The average stress in the matrix differs from the macro stress applied at infinity (Σ) by the existence of another average stress. So, we have :

$$\Sigma + \langle \sigma \rangle_{D-\Omega-\Omega_\mu} = \Sigma + \langle \sigma \rangle_{\Omega_m} = C_m : (E_0 + \bar{\epsilon}) \quad (3)$$

Where (E_0) denotes a uniform strain field and ($\bar{\epsilon}$) stands for the average disturbance in strain of the matrix due to the presence of all inclusions.

The stress in fibre and microcrack (inclusions) denoted respectively by (σ_f) and (σ_μ) can be written, using the Eshelby's solution:

$$\sigma_f = C_m : (E_0 + \bar{\epsilon} + (S_f - I) : \epsilon^*) \quad (4)$$

$$\sigma_\mu = C_m : [E_0 + \bar{\epsilon} + (S_\mu - I) : \epsilon_\mu^*] \quad (5)$$

(ϵ^*) denotes the eigenstrain (or transformation strain). (I) designates the fourth order identity tensor, and (S_f) et (S_μ) are the Eshelby tensor of fibre and microcrack respectively.

The transformation strains (ϵ^*) and (ϵ_μ^*) are obtained in ref.[6] as:

$$\epsilon^* = - [(C_f - C_m) : S_f + C_m]^{-1} (C_f - C_m) : (E_0 + \bar{\epsilon}) = L_f : (E_0 + \bar{\epsilon}) \quad (6)$$

$$\epsilon_\mu^* = [C_m - C_m : S_\mu]^{-1} C_m : (E_0 + \bar{\epsilon}) = L_\mu : (E_0 + \bar{\epsilon}) \quad (7)$$

The total macro strain tensor (E) of the equivalent material is obtained as the sum of the uniform strains and the all eigenstrains over the entire REV designated by (D), giving :

$$E = E_0 + \frac{1}{D} \int_{\Omega} \epsilon^* dv + \frac{1}{D} \int_{\Omega_\mu} \epsilon_\mu^* dv \quad (8)$$

Using the fourth order tensors (N) and (N_μ) defined by :

$$N = \frac{1}{D} \int_{\Omega} (S_f - I) : L_f dv \quad (9)$$

and
$$N_\mu = \frac{1}{D} \int_{\Omega_\mu} (S_\mu - I) : L_\mu dv \quad (10)$$

We have
$$E = [I + [\frac{1}{D} \int_{\Omega} L_f dv + \frac{1}{D} \int_{\Omega_\mu} L_\mu dv] [I + N + N_\mu]^{-1}] : E_0 \quad (11)$$

Consequently, the stiffness tensor of the material containing microcracks is obtained as:

$$\check{C}_C = C_m [I + \frac{1}{D} \int_{\Omega} L_f dv + \frac{1}{D} \int_{\Omega_\mu} L_\mu dv] [I + N + N_\mu]^{-1} \quad (12)$$

MECHANISMS OF TYPE (B) AND INTERFACIAL STRESS FIELD

The taking into account of interfacial decohesion together with the problems of fibre pull-out involves the determination of the stress and field at the interface. Considering Eqn (4), we have :

$$\sigma^{in} = C_m : E_0 + C_m : [(S_f - I) : \epsilon^* - \frac{1}{D} \int_{\Omega} (S_f - I) : \epsilon^* dv - \frac{1}{D} \int_{\Omega_{\mu}} (S_{\mu} - I) : \epsilon_{\mu}^* dv] \quad (13)$$

The stress field at the interface is expressed as a function of the stress field inside the inclusion, the transformation strain and the normal to the point considered at the interface.

The stress tensor outside the inclusion is given by Mura [7] Tendon and Weng [8] as:

$$\sigma^{out} = \sigma^{in} + C_m : \epsilon^{int} \quad (14)$$

where
$$\epsilon_{ke}^{int} = (- C_{pqmn}^m \epsilon_{mn}^* M_{kp} n_q n_e + \epsilon_{ke}^*) \quad (15)$$

with :
$$M_{kp} = \frac{1}{G_m} \left[\delta_{kp} - \frac{n_k n_p}{2(1-\nu_m)} \right] \quad (16)$$

(G_m, ν_m) are the shear modulus and the Poisson's ratio of the matrix respectively. (n_i) is the normal to the surface of the inclusion and (δ_{kp}) is the Kronecker symbol.

SIMULATION OF STRESS - STRAIN CURVES IN TENSILE TEST.

On the basis on the present model, behaviour simulation in the increase of the damage variable (β) corresponding to the matrix degradation and the evaluation of interfacial stress tensor, while taking into account the occurrence of matrix microcracks. Hence, for each orientation (θ), the microcrack density (β) is incremented due to the increase of the macro stress (Σ).

However, as illustrated by Eqn (13) the onset and the coalescence of these matrix microcracks may perturb locally the stress field in the inclusion and at the interface.

Furthermore, the introduction of damage mechanisms of type (B) in the damage model requires necessarily the evaluation of the maximum contribution (P_B) of these mechanisms, evaluated as detailed in the foregoing sections.

Hence, using the Eqn (13) the interfacial stress tensor corresponding to different values of the normal is obtained, while considering the simultaneously the effects of mechanisms (A) and (B).. Applying now a local interfacial criterion. In the case where it is checked for an orientation (θ), the interface is considered as completely debonded and the participation (P_B)_{max} has been reached locally. At this stage, a reduction coefficient is introduced. It enables the transformation of the reinforcement to an equivalent one, this may reduce the transformation strain (ϵ^*) and consequently the localisation tensor (\tilde{L}_f) such as :

$$\tilde{L}_f(\theta) = (1 - (P_B)_{max}) L_f(\theta) \quad (17)$$

So, while incrementing the damage variable, the transformed localisation tensor is thus introduced in the next computation of the stiffness tensor, as illustrated by the Eqn (13).

The increase of microcrack density represents the evolution of damage until the final stage of material degradation characterised by a critical value: ($\beta_{max} = (\nu\mu)_{max}$).

Figure (8) illustrates the quadratique regression corresponding to the function $\Sigma = \Sigma(S, \beta)$. This function connects the evolution of the density (β) to the increase of the applied stress (Σ) (S is the damage threshold). It is worth noting that the choice of this interpolation function is motivated by the non-linear behaviour in tensile loading. Furthermore, one observes that the evolution of the variable (β) pass by the three stages of damage evolution in the course of deformation. These damage stages correspond to the initiation phase, microcracks propagation and finally the accumulation and the generalisation of pseudo-delamination. This aspect has been observed on others types of composites with discontinuous reinforcement [6].

Figure (9) shows the simulated stress-strain tensile curves, as well as those obtained experimentally. It is fruitless to argue the good agreement between the theoretical results and the experimental curves. However, due to its penalising assumptions, it should be pointed out that the model prediction are less than experiments, notably at the end of damage evolution.

Fig. 7 Identification of the interpolation function $\Sigma=\Sigma(S,\beta)$ illustrating damage evolution.

Fig.8. Simulation of a tensile stress-strain curve and comparison with the experimental curves.

CONCLUSION

As conclusion, we can do the following concluding remarks:

(1) It emphasizes that the main initiator mechanism of the material degradation is the interface fibre/matrix decohesion. This damage mode induce a fibre pull-out reducing strongly the mechanical properties of composite. The use of both techniques acoustic emission and scanning electron microscopy observation enables the damage mechanisms investigation and classification according to their characteristic amplitudes and also to their nature.

(2) The results of the experimental methodology have been introduced in a micromechanical modelling. the latter has allowed us to predict the stiffness reduction and to simulate tensile curves. A good agreement between the theoretical results and the experimental values is obtained. moreover, it was shown that the non-linearity of material behaviour can be modelled using an quadratique interpolation representing the function $\Sigma=\Sigma(S,\beta)$

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